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Abstract book

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Prolonged survival in patient with IIIb stage squamous cell lung cancer – case report

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Introduction

Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) accounts for 80%–90% of lung cancers with a 5-year survival rate of 25%. Squamous cell carcinoma is the second most frequent type of NSCLC and is closely associated with cigarette smoking.

Case report

A 56 – year old female patient, smoker, ECOG 1, was diagnosed with stage IIIb (T4N2M0) squamous cell lung cancer in November 2016. Chest CT in November 2016 showed tumor in left hilus 5x3,7x5cm (APxLLxCC) with stenosis of left main bronchus, mediastinal lymphadenomagalgy, and athelectasis of S4 i S5 segment. As a first line of treatment patient received brachytherapy treatment (2x700 cGy) followed by concurrent chemoradiotherapy (50 Gy/25fr on tumor and mediastinal lymph nodes and Paclitaxel Carboplatin VII cycles). Control chest CT on July, 2017 suggested partial response and patient was followed up with additional diagnostic procedures. After progression which occurred in November 2018 patient received another brachytherapy treatment (2x700 cGy) in November 2018, followed with four cycles of second line chemotherapy Platina/Etoposid in February 2019, four cycles of third line chemotherapy Gemcitabin/Vinorelbin in November 2019. As a fifth line therapy patient is still receiving Atezolizumab.

Conclusion

Initially patient was diagnosed and staged as advanced disease stage IIIb after six year follow up and treatment patient has good performans status (ECOG 1) Multidisciplinary treatment, and rational application of multiple treatment measures can improve the quality of life of the patient with advanced lung cancer and prolong their survival.

Keywords: non-small cell lung cancer, multidisciplinary treatment, survival

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